

eDNAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Milestone 4: Gap analysis complete

Work Package 2

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Executive summary

This report evaluates current practices, challenges, and gaps in the reference libraries and repositories for environmental DNA (eDNA) in monitoring aquatic biodiversity, with a particular focus on Europe. The study finds that COX1, 16S, ITS, and 18S are the most common molecular markers in reference libraries, which mainly store data in public databases like NCBI GenBank, BOLD, and SILVA. However, metadata quality varies significantly, and metadata standards are frequently overlooked.

The inventory for eDNA repositories, compiled through extensive manual review, questionnaires, and automated paper mining, highlights 55 repositories but finds only 20% of these are highly relevant for broader use. Most repositories are regularly updated, though only a fraction provide annual updates or API support. Inconsistent metadata standards, incomplete taxonomic confidence indicators, and a lack of workflow details limit interoperability and accessibility.

The report concludes that progress is needed in metadata standardization, consistent taxonomic curation, and increased interoperability across repositories. Additionally, standardized workflows are critical to make eDNA data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). The report suggests encouraging open access, mandating eDNA data submission to repositories, and developing incentives for comprehensive data documentation to enhance data quality and usability across Europe's aquatic ecosystems.

Table of contents

1. Milestone 4: Gap analysis complete	4
A. Inventory, overview and gap analysis of DNA barcoding initiatives and reference libraries	4
1. Major gaps identified for Task 2.1	5
B. Inventory, overview and gap analysis of eDNA initiatives and repositories	7
1. Major gaps identified for Task 2.2	8
C. Task 2.3 Identification of workflows used currently for DNA-based biodiversity monitoring	9
1. Major gaps identifies for Task 2.3.....	9

1. Milestone 4: Gap analysis complete

The initial inventory analysis provided input for developing gap analyses concerning aquatic DNA barcoding projects across Europe and an inventory of repositories containing DNA barcode libraries.

A. Inventory, overview and gap analysis of DNA barcoding initiatives and reference libraries

This task concerns an inventory of European DNA barcoding projects and repositories containing DNA barcode reference libraries, identifying their geographical, ecological, and taxonomic coverages. Such libraries (*sensu* Weigand et al. 2019), containing reliable and taxonomically curated DNA sequences, are essential for biodiversity monitoring, as they allow the comparable use of ecological and biogeographical information on species. To identify DNA barcoding projects and DNA reference libraries of European aquatic biodiversity, the primary approach was a survey targeting peers who are or have been involved in relevant projects in Europe. Additionally, an experimental approach was investigated, using the development of a large language model (LLM) to process publications' content automatically. The collected content was explored using a list of search criteria the consortium members agreed upon, allowing for gap analysis, which refers to the process of identifying areas where data, resources, or coverage are lacking within existing DNA barcode datasets, as well as overlaps in (meta)data..

The survey was intended to gather information directly from crucial actors in developing DNA reference libraries of European aquatic biodiversity, increasing the likelihood of acquiring data from current projects that have yet to publish or deposit any information. Yet, its outcome is biased as it largely depended on the peers who responded to the survey. The experimental LLM-based approach aimed to provide an automated method for reviewing available publications, allowing for a more time-efficient data collection process. This approach also has limitations resulting from the content of the training dataset and the set of questions on which the LLM was based. Combining the two approaches facilitates a more comprehensive review of the existing libraries.

We received 49 replies, but only 38 originating from 33 institutions were accepted for downstream analysis. Specifically, only responses from institutions with projects fully or partially developed within the European territory (general project description) were considered, regardless of the participant's affiliation. Nevertheless, several replies pertained to multiple reference libraries, targeting different taxa and markers, and were considered independently whenever replies' details were allowed. Most contributions came from academic institutions followed by governmental bodies with minimal input from stakeholders, NGOs, and a research foundation. Projects were predominantly regional in scale (34%), while international projects accounted for 28%, national projects for 23%, and local projects for 13%. DNA reference libraries of marine organisms were the most common, followed by freshwater species, transitional waters, and groundwaters. Specimens were mainly sourced from captures in nature (55%), public collections (20%), and then private collections or cultures. The target taxa were primarily Eukarya, especially Metazoans (53%), with Prokaryotes (Archaea and Bacteria) accounting for 17%. Specimens were predominantly identified based on morphology (63%), while 25% used both morphological and molecular methods. Highly experienced identifiers (Level I; 71%) were the main contributors, focusing on species or genus-level identifications (accounting for 70% of cases). WoRMS was the primary reference source for taxonomy in marine and transition waters, whereas WoRMS, NCBI, and GBIF dominated for freshwaters. Most DNA reference libraries included fewer than 200 species; most contained less than 500 sequenced specimens. Some projects reported sequencing between 1,000 and 3,000 specimens. Most participants (72%) reported keeping all specimens as vouchers, stored primarily in academic or museum collections, with ethanol being the commonest storage preservative, followed by sub-zero temperatures. DNA aliquots were commonly stored under sub-zero temperatures, notably at -20 °C (59%) and -80 °C (24%). Various molecular markers were used in reference libraries for aquatic organisms. COX1 was the most targeted marker (30%), likely corresponding to sequences of the animal barcode region. The second most applied marker was mitochondrial 16S rRNA (15%), followed by the nuclear 18S rRNA (10%) and ITS (7%). The 16S rRNA and the 12S rRNA genes were also targets for

bacteria and fish reference libraries. However, given that rRNA genes lack a standard target region (e.g. 12S, 18S, mitochondrial 16S), it is impossible to ascertain if the reference libraries correspond to the same marker region. Most projects (82%) had deposited at least some DNA reference sequences, primarily in public databases, such as BOLD and NCBI (both 41%). Metadata was deposited for 91% of sequences; however, metadata standards were not commonly followed (55% did not adhere to standards). The most frequently deposited metadata included project identification, GPS coordinates, voucher ID and location, person collecting and identifying, and depth/altitude. The collection date was mentioned only in two cases. The deposition of specimen images was reported in about half of the libraries. Among the sequence-associated metadata, the molecular marker and sequenced region were also frequently recorded; other elements, such as PCR and sequencing primers, trace files and sequencing platforms, were provided in less than half of the cases. Taxonomic curation procedures were applied in nearly 65% of the libraries, while about one-third of phylogenetic congruence checks were reported.

From over 850 papers processed by the LLM, the most reported markers, ordered by prevalence, were COX1, 16S (no discrimination between prokaryotic and mitochondrial), ITS and 18S. Other sixteen molecular markers/regions were barely reported. A total of 55 reference databases were found in the analysed papers, of which only 20% were relevant (more than 10 reports). NCBI GenBank and SILVA were highlighted, both with ca. 38% of the reports, followed by BOLD, UNITE, EMBL, RDP, PR2, and GreenGenes, which altogether accounted for 42%.

Regarding the repositories, a list of 25 public repositories containing DNA reference records for several molecular markers and a wide range of aquatic taxa was compiled. Twenty-one of these were qualified for the following analysis. Most of the repositories are updated periodically, but only 5 of them are updated annually. Twenty repositories cover all aquatic environments, while only four focus on marine waters, and one contains only freshwater records. Half of the repositories store data on multiple molecular markers, with 16S rRNA data being the most abundant, followed by COI and 18S rRNA. However, 16S data pertains to two distinct markers, namely the prokaryotic and mitochondrial 16S rRNA genes. Most repositories, such as sample collection and sequence protocols, lack detailed workflow information. Nearly all repositories use some taxonomic curation, but most lack confidence levels for taxonomic identification. Most repositories have a standardised structure but usually do not offer API, desktop or console support. Four repositories lack web interfaces. FASTA is the most common format in which the data can be downloaded from the databases.

In conclusion, while reasonable progress has been made in Europe to build reference libraries for aquatic organisms, there is a considerable dispersion of initiatives and uncoordinated efforts. This resulted in reference libraries with varied levels of comprehensiveness, metadata content, taxonomic curation, auditability, accessibility and interoperability. Hence, there is a strong need for standardised metadata practices, rigorous and harmonised full-curation procedures, and improved data-sharing mechanisms. Our results help identify the significant deficiencies in the content and format of reference library data, thereby contributing to the design of broadly applicable recommendations to improve data quality and adherence to FAIR principles. Enhancing these aspects will be essential for advancing biodiversity monitoring and research efforts across European aquatic ecosystems.

1. Major gaps identified for Task 2.1

Specimen source, taxonomic identification and processing	
Gap	Description
Unequal coverage of aquatic ecosystems.	Most of the data available for freshwater and marine waters, limited information from transitional waters and scarce from groundwaters.
Diverse sources of taxonomy in different libraries.	Sources of cross-reference source for taxonomy were diverse and dependent on the environment or taxa used. For example, WoRMS was the main choice for marine and transition waters, whereas

	for freshwaters it was WoRMS along with NCBI and GBIF that dominated.
Different methods and ranks of identification for Metazoa versus microbial libraries.	Morphology-based, species-level taxonomic identification of specimens was the most used approach for metazoan-dominated repositories, while the molecular identification and genus- or family-level identification were associated with microbial repositories.
Little information on the libraries' quantitative data.	There were few replies with quantitative data on the number of the specimens and species included in the reference barcode libraries. The available replies indicate that most repositories have less than 200 species and below 500 specimens.
Considerable variation among taxonomic groups in terms of the degree of coverage.	Overall, libraries for freshwater organisms appear to be more complete than for those inhabiting marine and transitional waters, which have low representation of some dominant and diverse groups (e.g. gastropods). Globally, fish species are much better represented than invertebrates. There are still many gaps in non-indigenous marine invertebrate species, which due to their potential environmental impact deserve particular attention in marine biomonitoring programs. Finally, the gap evaluation for microbial organisms is far more complex than for macro-organisms.
Limited information on voucher storage conditions.	Specimens are primarily stored in academic or museum collections. Ethanol was the most frequently used storage preservative, especially for freshwater and marine specimens, followed by sub-zero temperatures. However most replies did not mention the ethanol concentration, which may have a strong impact in the ability to recover DNA in the future.
DNA sequence data, metadata and data management	
Gap	Description
Broad diversity of molecular markers used as barcodes.	Although COX1 (formal animal barcode region at the 5' end of the gene) was the most represented marker for each environment, 19 other markers are also used and deposited in databases, depending on the taxonomic group and environment. For example, 16SrNA is prevalent in transitional and fresh waters, while 12SrNA is used predominantly for fish and other vertebrates. For such markers, lacking a standard barcode region, publicly available sequences compose a mosaic of segments from different regions within the gene, often restricted to the few base pairs delimited by the most commonly used metabarcoding primers. This makes it hard to appreciate the taxonomic coverage and effectiveness of the reference library for general DNA-based monitoring.
Lack of established metadata standards.	Only about half of the reviewed libraries followed metadata standards, the majority of which referred to BOLD and Darwin core. The most

	frequently deposited metadata included project identification, GPS coordinates, voucher ID and location, person collecting and identifying specimens, and depth/altitude.
Relevant metadata missing in most cases	Collection date, which is highly relevant for specimens collected from the wild, was rarely mentioned. Extremely relevant metadata, such as images of specimens, PCR and sequencing primers, trace files and sequencing platforms were provided in less than half of the cases.
Lack of generally recognised minimal criteria for sequence acceptance in reference libraries.	The sequence acceptance procedure in the libraries was primarily based on sequence quality, then sequence length, and also metadata traceability, but the latter in less than one third of the cases.
Lack of uniform taxonomic curation procedures.	Taxonomic curation procedures were applied in just under 65% of the libraries. The curation procedures varied considerably and were not equivalent. Phylogenetic congruence checks were only reported for about one third of the libraries with curation procedures. A general appraisal and recommendations for reference libraries auditing annotation and curation systems are needed.
DNA sequence data repositories	
Gap	Description
Non-generalized storage of multiple molecular markers	Only half of the repositories store data on multiple molecular markers.
Lack of regular yearly updates.	Most of the repositories were updated periodically, but only few annually.
Variable or inexistent metadata standards	Only two databases have mandatory metadata. Merely a third of the repositories provide GPS coordinates for specimen records.
Lack of workflow information.	Most repositories lack detailed workflow information such as sample collection and sequencing protocols.
Scarcity of confidence levels for taxonomic identifications	Nearly all repositories use some taxonomic curation but, at the same time, most lack confidence levels for taxonomic identifications.
Lack of API standards.	Most repositories do not offer API, desktop or console support. Some lack any web interfaces.

B. Inventory, overview and gap analysis of eDNA initiatives and repositories

The outcome of this task is an inventory of the ongoing and completed environmental DNA (eDNA) initiatives and repositories, identifying their geographical, ecological and taxonomic coverages. It includes a brief description of the methodologies used to perform the inventorying.

The inventory was sought in three different ways: (1) manual review of 29 resources (eDNA and reference libraries) by the bioinformatics team for 40 properties, (2) a questionnaire sent out to eDNA research teams, for which (60) responses were neatly collated, (3) automated(LLM) mining of scientific papers. This inventory allowed us to obtain a good overview of the current initiatives and databases used for eDNA data sharing and publication and identify the main gaps and areas for improvement. The input and this work was performed by many people of different academic backgrounds bringing their expertise

to bear. Findings of this report are input to other tasks notably T3.2 and their iterative feedback improved this report. Please see Table 1 for the main identified gaps.

1. Major gaps identified for Task 2.2

Gap	Description
eDNA raw sequence data is scattered through many repositories	Much eDNA raw sequence data is external to INSDC archives, which makes it difficult to find or reuse data. We were not able to determine exactly how much, but reviews have estimated up to 50% and this is supported by our LLM investigation.
eDNA sequence storage DBs reference only found in 50-77% of scientific papers	Related to the previous gap, in the LLM investigation at best 77% of scientific papers contain the eDNA sequence storage location.
Each repository has its own API and little consistency of each API	eDNA raw sequence accession ids are hard to query for or to retrieve from many portals or even their APIs, making federated queries challenging
Missing important general sample or sequence related metadata	One third of repositories in the survey are missing any general sample or sequence related metadata e.g. GPS coordinate or library_strategy
Many repositories have no stated processed metadata standards	41/61 repositories of the survey had no stated processed metadata standards.
Some repositories are using global metadata standards, but many are not	DwC(e.g. OBIS and GBIF) and GSC MixS(e.g. INSDC) are the most common where there are global standards. Indeed there is a MixS TDWG DwC mapping task force. Where eDNA data is buried in papers or in Dryad etc., it is less likely to be using global standards.
Difficult to query for aquatic environmental samples/raw sequence records from the INSDC archives	There are multiple parameters needed to get aquatic environmental samples from the INSDC archives in terms of coverage and accuracy.
Inconsistency of data formats besides fasta(albeit variable) and fastq	Inconsistent formats are one aspect that reduces interoperability and reusability.
Barcode gene identification is inconsistent in INSDC	In the INSDC, barcode gene nomenclature for eDNA aquatic samples are rarely captured in the "target_gene" field and we determined that only 20% recorded in the study description or title.
INSDC users sometimes using generic and not aquatic specific checklists	Generic sample checklists with less mandatory information are available at INSDC databases. Users sometimes tend to use these checklists instead of the more specific and metadata rich checklists, which limits data searchability and reusability.
Sampling and archives have been disproportionately lacking from Eastern Europe.	In terms of ecological environments across Europe, there is much diversity of aquatic environments in Europe, in terms of marine, freshwater, ground and brackish. There are eDNA samples in the major seas surrounding Europe and in many countries.
The INSDC raw sequence only gets the taxonomy id initially provided on submission.	The INSDC only gets the taxID when sequences have been uploaded, it is not up to date when new taxonomies arise or what gets determined by taxonomic identification.
Generally difficult to specifically find eDNA records.	It is hard in most resources to even get a count of eDNA records. It is sometimes not clear what is a raw eDNA sequence record, what is processed and how to query for such.

C. Task 2.3 Identification of workflows used currently for DNA-based biodiversity monitoring

The outcome of this task is an inventory of the workflows used in European aquatic eDNA-based biodiversity monitoring. The inventory is based on manual research of guidelines and standards, a manual search of reports from commissioned eDNA-based biomonitoring, the questionnaire survey developed within this work package, and the automated collection of metadata from BioSamples in INSCD databases.

The conclusions highlight the need for standardised workflows and metadata requirements to support the scalability of eDNA monitoring in Europe and to ensure data adheres to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). Metadata and Data Storage: Current practices for storing European eDNA-related data in databases like BioSamples, GBIF, and OBIS were reviewed. Data from commissioned eDNA biomonitoring is seldom stored in publicly accessible databases. Written reports from smaller consultancy companies are often private; if they are, they lack bibliographic indexes. Compilation of metadata from European samples stored in public databases showed that metadata frequently needs to be completed, particularly regarding sampling protocols and DNA extraction methods. Geographic data is usually not in a standardised format - the lack of standardised metadata hampers data reusability. The report identifies several critical gaps, including (1) limited accessibility to national protocols published only in local languages, (2) inconsistent submission of eDNA data to repositories, leading to difficulties in finding and using this information, (3) the need for harmonised standards to ensure comparability across datasets from different regions and institutions. The document stresses the importance of promoting open access to national monitoring protocols and international cooperation on standard development. It suggests exploring whether submission of eDNA data to repositories can be mandated and highlights a need for incentives for proper documentation and metadata compliance.

1. Major gaps identifies for Task 2.3

Scientific and practitioner community	
Gap	Description
Internal protocols and guidelines not published or not findable	Many are published in national language only. A comprehensive review of workflows and guidelines is difficult.
Lack of method standards	Plurality of methods, risk of incomparable data and problems in harmonising European-level data sets.
Data submission	
Gap	Description
Data from commissioned eDNA biomonitoring is seldom accessible to the wider scientific community	Reports from commissioned eDNA biomonitoring are often published as "grey literature" (without bibliographic indexing), and/or in native languages. The data are often not submitted to repositories or biodiversity portals. Limits findability and reusability.
Occurrences based on eDNA seldom registered in biodiversity repositories	Manual search of Gbif and OBIS revealed that so far a limited number of data sets based on aquatic eDNA from Europe have been submitted (altogether c. 10 data sets).
Metadata describing the eDNA workflow of sequencing data in the INSDC is usually scarce	BioSample metadata supplied by the submitter seldom contains information on sampling protocol, size fraction or DNA isolation protocol. Geographic coordinates are not in a standardised format. This limits the reusability of the data.
Data standards	
Gap	Description

The definitions of types of data records in the INSDC databases is unclear (e.g., a BioSample vs. a Sequencing run or Nucleotide record).	It is not always clear which type of metadata should be associated with each type of data record.
Low granularity in the Darwin core DNA-derived data metadata related to bioinformatic processing	For instance, there is not a designated field for the sequence denoising method.

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